

Visa Application Support

Many participants attending the Open Science Retreat 2025 required visas to enter Switzerland. Given the short timeline between sending out acceptance notifications in late February and the retreat start date in mid-April, timely support was essential to ensure successful visa applications.

To facilitate the process, the acceptance emails included a prompt for those needing visa assistance to contact the organizing team. Respondents were redirected to an online form designed to collect the information required to issue an official invitation letter. A screenshot of the form is included below.

Using a pre-prepared template, the organizing team generated personalized invitation letters and sent them directly to participants. In some cases, either upon request from the participants or contact from the Swiss authorities, the letters were also sent to the relevant Swiss embassies to support the applications. Participants who needed to provide confirmation of accommodation received additional letters upon request.¹ The organizing team also provided support in filling out certain sections of the visa application form, pertaining to the contact and official details of the inviter. For a few individuals with extended travel dates due to flight availability, invitation letter dates were adjusted accordingly, and they submitted proof of extra accommodation (e.g., booking receipts) with their application. A sample accommodation letter is also provided. We also sent a copy of the program of the retreat.

Swiss embassy appointments were generally accessible, and visa processing was typically completed within a few days to a week after submission. Most participants who requested assistance were able to obtain their visas in time. Only two potential participants were unable to do so. Delays resulted from applying through a non-Swiss Schengen embassy and trying to get a visa appointment in a large metropolitan area in the UK.

Despite the tight time frame, the proactive support process helped ensure that nearly all participants requiring visas were able to attend the retreat.

¹ In this case the Digital Research Academy (DRA) provided these letters and not the accommodation venue directly because DRA was the organization who booked the accommodations at the venue and assigned the rooms to participants. Normally, hotel booking confirmations would be enough for a visa application.

Visa Letter Info Request Form

OSR25 Visa Invitation Letter

Hi there!

We look forward to welcoming you to OSR25 at Beatenberg, CH. Please fill out the following form so that we can provide a letter to support your visa application. We look forward to spending a relaxing and creative week with you in the Swiss Alps. All data entered will remain confidential and will be used only for the visa letter.

* Indicates required question

Email *

Your email

Full Name (First, Last) *

Your answer

Date of Birth *

Date

dd.mm.yyyy

Nationality (as indicated on your passport) *

Your answer

Passport Number *

Your answer

Residential address *

Your answer

Embassy Name *

Embassy Address

Embassy Email-ID

Example:

Embassy of Switzerland,

New Delhi,

110 021, India

newdelhi.visa@eda.admin.ch

Your answer

A copy of your responses will be emailed to the address you provided.

Submit

Page 1 of 1

Clear form

Sample Invitation Letter

Embassy of Switzerland

[ADDRESS OF SWISS EMBASSY]

[ADDRESS OF SWISS EMBASSY]

[EMAIL OF SWISS EMBASSY]

Zurich, [DATE OF LETTER]

Invitation letter for [PARTICIPANT FULL NAME], born [PARTICIPANT BIRTH DATE],
[PARTICIPANT NATIONALITY e.g. Kenyan/Egyptian/Indian/etc.] National, Passport No
[#####], residing in [PARTICIPANT HOME ADDRESS]

Dear Madam,

Dear Sir,

On behalf of the Open Innovation in Life Science association (OILS), we wish to extend this invitation to [PARTICIPANT NAME] to attend the 3rd Open Science Retreat, to be held in Beatenberg, Switzerland from 13-17th April 2025.

Open Innovation in Life Sciences association, under the umbrella of Life Science Zurich (University of Zurich (UZH) and Eidgenössische Technische Hochschule Zurich (ETHZ)), is a voluntary association that aims to promote openness in science. This year, the Open Science Retreat is co-organised by OILS along with the Digital Research Academy and the Center for Reproducible Research, University of Zurich. During this one week, participants will get the chance to engage in scientific discussions and develop new ideas in an unconference model.

Therefore, we would like to invite [PARTICIPANT NAME] to join us in person for the Open Science Retreat on 13th April 2025. [PARTICIPANT NAME] was selected from a pool of applicants after careful consideration and has received stipends supported by the Swiss National Science Foundation Scientific Exchange Grant that will cover participation fees including 4-nights of accommodations and travel to the event.

[PARTICIPANT NAME] will stay at the Gästehaus Beatenberg Spirenwaldstrasse 356 CH-3803 Beatenberg for 4 nights/5 days.

We hope that you will be able to issue a visa for [PARTICIPANT NAME]'s visit to Beatenberg. If you have any further questions, please do not hesitate to contact us.

Sincerely,

[SIGNATURES OF INVITING INSTITUTION]

Sample Accommodation Letter

Embassy of Switzerland

[ADDRESS OF SWISS EMBASSY]

[ADDRESS OF SWISS EMBASSY]

[EMAIL OF SWISS EMBASSY]

Date: [DD.MM.YYYY]

Accommodation Reservation Confirmation for [PARTICIPANT NAME] - Open Science Retreat

Dear Sir/Madam,

We are writing to formally confirm that [PARTICIPANT NAME] at [PARTICIPANT HOME ADDRESS] has been provided accommodation at the Gästehaus Beatenberg, located at Spirenwaldstrasse 356, CH-3803 Beatenberg, Switzerland, for the duration of the Open Science Retreat (April 13-17, 2025).

The **Digital Research Academy** has booked the venue for the retreat and is responsible for managing room assignments in collaboration with Gästehaus Beatenberg. [PARTICIPANT NAME]'s accommodation is confirmed for **four nights and five days** as part of their participation in this event.

Should you require any further information, please do not hesitate to contact us.

All the best,

[SIGNATURES OF ACCOMMODATION PROVIDER]